

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING CHILDREN WITH HEARING DISABILITY

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Abstract. *The benefits of information technology for children with disabilities' academic development are covered in the article. Information technologies may be used to help teach children with hearing impairment the principles of developmental education, improve the ways in which the educational process is organized, and make the transition from mechanical assimilation to the mastery of real skills that allow one to independently acquire new knowledge. The article analyzes the structure and technology support of the development of vocational education for students with hearing impairment. Particularly, the instructional and rehabilitation technologies of the aforementioned group of students' contents have been mentioned.*

Keywords: *developmental education, individualization and differentiation of the educational process, effective organization, quality of education, improvement of perception methods, correction, hearing-saving technologies.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Equipping educational process with new information technologies is one of the requirements for the modernization of education at this time.

Teachers now have the ability to qualitatively alter the subject matter, instructional strategies, and organizational structures of the classroom due to the penetration of modern digital technology. The goal of these technologies in education is to improve the quality of education at all levels of the educational system, as well as to humanize, individualize, intensify, and enhance the learning experience for students in the information society. According to Robert I.W., the following are the primary instructional objectives of utilizing contemporary information technologies:

Intensification of the educational process at all levels for the following reasons:

- Increasing cognitive activity;
- Deepening interdisciplinary connections;
- Increasing the volume and optimizing the search for the required information;
- Improving the effectiveness and quality of the learning process.

Many teachers are more willingly incorporating them into their methodical approach as a result of the significant impact that contemporary information technologies have on the educational process.

Education of children with disabilities provides for the creation of special educational and developmental environments that provide adequate conditions for education within special educational standards and equal opportunities with ordinary children. In recent years, computer technology has been widely used in correctional education systems.

The comprehensive development of deaf students and their preparation for life is one of the main tasks of schools for deaf children. Solution This task cannot be fully solved if the student does not have a good command of the oral language, especially its oral form. Contact with deaf

people requires the ability of deaf people to understand the language of the person addressed to them and the ability to speak clearly and understandably to others. It is well known that communication is the most important means of obtaining diverse information. In modern societies, information exchange is arguably primarily driven by computer technology, but this does not exclude verbal communication in general.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Effective social policies towards persons with disabilities - one of the most important indicators of both the level of development and the civilization and humanity of civil society. Finally, the true formation of human civilization begins with what A. Schweitzer called 'respect for life', 'respect for life: respect for one's own and one another's life' [1].

Social policies for persons with disabilities should be based on their empowerment and respect for their civil rights. The right to education plays a special role in this.

The main causes of unequal treatment of persons with disabilities in higher education are: Lack of barrier-free educational and rehabilitation environments and developed infrastructure. Inefficiencies of modern teaching technology, telecommunication networks and distance learning methods. Lack of special technical equipment [2].

Deaf people have limitations in communication, orientation, learning, and employment and are effectively deaf. The educational system of higher education for persons with disabilities must fully or partially compensate for the limitations of their life activities so that persons with disabilities can compete on an equal footing in the labor market.

Creating educational and rehabilitation environments for hearing opportunities for people with disabilities includes:

Developing professional training in special skills; Building barrier-free communication environments; Ensuring health protection; Providing gradual rehabilitation assistance in the educational process;

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the process of shaping the language pronunciation of deaf students, there is a need to improve the implementation of differentiated approaches in contemporary contexts. Modern information and communication technology (ICT) offer the perfect opportunity for this.

Unlike traditional technological teaching tools, ICT not only saturates students with a large number of ready-made, strictly selected and well-organized knowledge, but also enhances their intellectual and creative abilities. Develop and enhance your ability to acquire new knowledge independently. Using information from a variety of sources, it considers each child's individual characteristics and provides teachers and defect scholars with an excellent opportunity to distinguish between the materials presented in the classroom in a minimal amount of time.

When working with children, information technology is considered part of the overall learning system. Combining not only the development of speech and hearing, but also the development of the personality in general. With the implementation of new information technologies for the development of students' pronunciation skills in the educational process, activation of process learning, for the development of learning ideas, improve the pace of education, increase the amount of information perceived, and allow student to work independently.

Existing training programs:

Visible speech, timelines, etc. complement the personal development of the teacher, depending on the tasks provided. Training programs can use different forms of visibility to encourage different ways of organizing and presenting theoretical material in the form of tables and graphs. In addition to static information, it also uses colors, graphics, flicker, sounds, pictograms, illustrated "animations", etc. to demonstrate various sound phenomena in dynamics).

The Microsoft PowerPoint program is most commonly used in the work of the Defector teacher when creating class presentations on interactive whiteboards. It belongs to the so-called class of multimedia technologies, as it allows us to combine the functions of text and graphics editors, animation (moving objects), sound and video. This method of information presentation, applied to remedial learning conditions, is particularly important because it considers the details of each category of students and allows the use of different security her analyzers.

The methodological value of Microsoft PowerPoint is not limited to this. As already mentioned, this program is used for creating presentations. A presentation is a series of slides or "electronic pages" (using the analogy of a book). At the same time, the algorithm (or scheme) for constructing the presentation structure is arbitrarily configurable according to the needs of the presentation creator. Presentation structures can be linear, branched, cyclic, and mixed.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS

The use of bright pictures, interesting and unusual tasks included in the presentation of lessons helps to increase the interest of schoolchildren in their native language, allows them to familiarize themselves with the study material in a fun way and provides wide opportunities for self-control and self-management. To do. Educational considerations

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

During the course of training, deaf and deaf people create a new functional system that was lacking at the start of training: hearing.

A speech hearing was formed. The presence of speech hearing makes it possible to build the process of correcting the student's pronunciation according to the laws of formation of the pronunciation side of the hearing child's speech. The basis for the acquisition of oral language by deaf students is the rapid development of auditory perception, in which the weights of auditory components are identified.

Continuous improvement in speech comprehension has a great impact on the intellectual development and personality of deaf and hard of hearing people. The ability to listen to the interlocutor and understand for himself their capacity and willingness to establish auditory contact in all circumstances, the freedom of communication with auditory fellow students and teachers in the integrated space of the university and in society. These are the results of years of research into the emergence and development of speech hearing in people with hearing impairments.

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